

Extraction studies of Pb^{II} from salicylate media using neutral organophosphorous extractant, Cyanex-923 in toluene

S. M. Ghag and S. D. Pawar*

Department of Chemistry, Siddharth College of Arts, Science & Commerce, Dr. D. N. Road, Fort, Mumbai-400 001, India

E-mail : sureshpawar_2004@rediffmail.com, ghag.snehal@yahoo.com

Manuscript received 22 May 2008, revised 8 July 2008, accepted 29 July 2008

Abstract : The neutral extractant, Cyanex-923 has been used for the extraction of Pb^{II} from sodium salicylate media. This metal ion was found to be quantitatively extracted with Cyanex-923 in toluene in the pH range 6–7 and from the organic phase it is stripped with 1.5 M HCl solution. The effect of pH, sodium salicylate concentration, reagent concentration, equilibration period, diluents, diverse ions and stripping agent on the extraction of Pb^{II} has been studied.

Keywords : Cyanex-923, extraction, sodium salicylate, Pb^{II}.

Introduction

Literature survey reveals that a large number of extraction methods are available for the extraction of lead^I. However, these methods have several limitations, such as strict pH control, longer extraction period, critical temperature control and severe interference.

In the present work the extraction of Pb^{II} from salicylate media using Cyanex-923 in toluene has been carried out. The proposed method was then employed for the analysis of lead(II) in alloy samples like leaded bronze and tin based white metal.

Procedure :

An aliquot containing 50 µg of Pb^{II} and 0.005 M sodium salicylate (10 ml) was equilibrated with equal volume of 0.01 M Cyanex-923 in toluene. The pH of the resulting solution was adjusted at 6.0 with dilute HCl and NH₄OH and shaken for 10 min. The metal loaded organic phase was stripped with 1.5 M HCl and was determined spectrophotometrically by the PAR method at 510 nm². All the experiments were carried out at room temperature.

Results and discussion

Effect of pH, sodium salicylate and reagent concentration on percentage extraction of Pb^{II} with Cyanex-923 in toluene :

Extraction of Pb^{II} containing 0.005 M sodium salicy-

late was carried out in the pH range of 1.0–7.0 with Cyanex-923 in toluene. With increase in pH extraction becomes more efficient and found to be quantitative in the pH range 6.0–7.0. Hence all extractions of Pb^{II} with Cyanex-923 were carried out at a fixed pH of 6.0. The effect of sodium salicylate concentration on the percentage extraction of Pb^{II} with 0.01 M Cyanex-923 in toluene was studied in the sodium salicylate range from 2.5 × 10⁻⁵–0.1 M. As the sodium salicylate concentration increases, the extraction improves and becomes quantitative in the range 0.005–0.1 M with Cyanex-923 in toluene. Hence all the extractions were carried out at 0.005 M sodium salicylate with Cyanex-923.

Extraction of Pb^{II} was also carried out by varying the reagent concentration (1.0 × 10⁻¹–5.0 × 10⁻⁴ M) keeping other parameters like pH, period of equilibration, diluent and temperature constant. Extraction was found to be effective with increase in reagent concentration. The distribution ratio increases with increase in the reagent concentration. The extraction of Pb^{II} was quantitative in the range of 0.1–0.01 M Cyanex-923 in toluene, hence all the extractions of Pb^{II} were carried at fixed reagent concentration of 0.01 M.

Effect of diluents, period of equilibration, stripping agent and diverse ions on percentage extraction of Pb^{II} with Cyanex-923 in toluene :

Various aromatic and aliphatic diluents like toluene, chloroform, carbontetrachloride, benzene, cyclohexane,

n-hexane and xylene were employed for extraction of Pb^{II}. The extraction of Pb^{II} with Cyanex-923 was found to be quantitative with all the diluents except xylene. Toluene was used as best diluent for Cyanex-923 extractant because of better phase separation.

Extraction equilibrium was studied for different periods of shaking ranging from 1–20 min. It was observed that 5 min of shaking period was sufficient for quantitative extraction of Pb^{II} with 0.01 M Cyanex-923 in toluene. However there was no adverse effect by increasing the extraction period upto 30 min. Lead(II) was stripped out from its metal loaded organic phases with different strength of mineral acids like HCl, HNO₃, H₂SO₄. It was found that quantitative stripping of Pb^{II} from the organic phase was observed with 1.5–2.0 M HCl, 1.5 M HNO₃ and 1.5 M H₂SO₄. The effect of various diverse ions on the extraction of Pb^{II} was studied with Cyanex-923 in toluene. The tolerance limit of individual foreign ions was set so that error in percentage recovery was not more than ±2%. Alkali and alkaline earth metal ions like Na^I, Li^I, K^I, Mg^{II} (1 : 20) are highly tolerated. The other metal ions like Ca^{II}, In^{III}, Tl^{III}, Mo^{VI} interfere in ratio 1 : 15, Pd^{II}, Pt^{IV}, Rh^{III}, Hg^{II}, Br^I, I⁻, Cl⁻, Al^{III}, Ga^{III} in ratio 1 : 10, Cr^{III}, Ni^{II}, Mn^{II}, Fe^{III}, Zn^{II} in the ratio 1 : 5 and Cs^I, Cu^{II}, Sb^{III}, Bi^{III} in the ratio 1 : 3. EDTA and disodium tartrate interfere with the system.

The proposed methods were employed for the analysis of lead(II) in alloys like leaded bronze and tin based

white metal. 100 mg of each alloy was dissolved in 15 cm³ of nitric acid and evaporated to dryness. The residue was treated with water and precipitated metastannic acid was filtered and then washed with hot dilute nitric acid and water. The filtrates, thus obtained were diluted to 25 cm³. Aliquots of these filtrates were analyzed for lead separately by the proposed method described above. The percentage recovery of lead by the above method in the leaded bronze and tin based white metals is 99.2% and 99.3% respectively.

Conclusion :

The results indicate that Cyanex-923, commercially available phosphine oxide, extract Pb^{II} quantitatively from its aqueous solution in the pH range 6.0–7.0 from sodium salicylate media.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Cytec Industries Inc., Canada for supplying cyanex-923 as gift sample.

References

1. J. Wang, *Huaxue Tanbon.*, 1986, **7**, 37; T. Honjo, S. Yashima and T. Kiba, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1973, **46**, 3722; M. Erdeia and B. V. Gromov, *Trudy. Mosk. Khim-technol. Inst.*, 1968, **58**, 71; B. Raman and V. M. Shinde, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1989, **36**, 469.
2. A. A. Yadav and S. M. Khopkar, *Talanta*, 1971, **18**, 833.